

Distributional criteria for identifying formulas in Finnic oral poetry

Maciej Janicki, Kati Kallio, Mari Sarv, Eetu Mäkelä

The digitised collections of Finnic oral poetry present exceptional material for studying oral tradition. According to the oral-formulaic theory, in oral tradition singers recreate the poems during performance relying on a store of composition units of various lengths. The formula was defined by Lord as "a group of words, employed repeatedly under the same metric conditions to express a certain idea". In the framework of oral-formulaic theory the concept of formula has got a wider meaning of recurrent units of various lengths.

Recently, we have been applying a clustering based on cosine similarity of character bigrams to identify equivalent poetic lines across dialectal and orthographic variation. Building up on that, in this paper we explore quantitative criteria for identifying formulas, starting on the level of a single line.

The first obvious criterion is frequency. Furthermore, we introduce a measure of "stereotypy" as entropy of the distribution of line over high-level context, which is approximated by automatic text clustering. Finally, we apply a statistical co-occurrence metric (log-likelihood ratio) to identify lines frequently occurring together. We examine the capability of the method to identify parallel lines and multi-line formulas.

Introduction

In the research of oral poetry, the classic definition of formula is "a group of words which is regularly employed under the same metrical conditions to express a given idea" (Parry 1930, 80), defining the formula as a 1) recurrent unit in terms of 2) combination of particular words which 3) express a particular idea and 4) fit into particular positions of a particular poetic metre. As Karl Reichl (2022, 27) notes, Parry was, originally, defining formulas only in Homeric poetry. Before him, the word, mostly in Latin, was typically employed in the context of law and without poetic or

metrical connotations as a “set form of words in which something is defined, stated, or declared, or which is prescribed by authority or custom to be used on some ceremonial occasion” (OED: formula).

What Parry did, continuing his analysis with Albert Lord (1960), transformed the understandings of oral poetry. Conducting field work with singers of Serbo-Croatian epics, they understood that here, each singer composed their story anew in each performance on the basis of formulas, themes (groups of ideas that can be expressed in various ways) and traditional story-lines (“flexible plan of themes”, “stable skeleton of narrative”). Later, it was elaborated that the characteristics or the quality of the formulas and the ways and amounts of using them actually depended on at least singer, genre, and tradition (Foley 1995), and formulas may be understood to exist also in non-metrical genres (Reichl 2023). The concept of formula has been employed for different poetic and prose traditions and for different research questions, resulting in various elaborations and interpretations of the concept. (See Frog & Lamb 2022; Foley 1988; Harvilahti 1992a.)

In this paper we study formulaic language in Finnic oral poetry. The digitization of vast materials from archival collections in Finland and Estonia has enabled computational and quantitative studies on a large scale. We seek to delimit the concept of ‘formula’ in quantitative terms, by studying the properties of frequent text units – lines in the current research. By studying the distribution of lines over contexts, which can be approximated by automatic text clustering, we are able to distinguish truly ‘formulaic’ lines (occurring in varying contexts) from fixed fragments of specific texts. Further, we identify two-line formulas by means of commonly used statistical co-occurrence measures.

Finnic oral poetry

The Finnic languages spoken in the Northeastern Baltic sea region: Estonian, Seto, Votic, Ingrian, Karelian, Ludic and Finnish, share a common poetic system, variously called runosongs, *regilaul*, Finnic alliterative tetrameter or Kalevalaic poetry. Same poetic metre was used for various different genres such as epics, historical songs, lyric, ritual songs, proverbs, mocking songs, lullabies and riddles. (See Kallio et al.

2017). One poetic metre for various genres made it easy to use formulas or motifs typical of one genre embedded in another (e.g. Tarkka 2017).

Due to historical and national reasons, Finnic oral poetry was recorded in great numbers by the 19th and early 20th century scholars in Finland and Estonia. Currently, we have c. 250 000 texts from Finnish and Estonian archives relating to this tradition in digital form, sharing similar text and metadata structure. In the project ‘FILTER’¹ we have combined these into a single database (see Kallio et al. 2023).

The texts exhibit great variation in terms of languages and dialects (phonetics, vocabulary, morphology etc.), orthography (except for the standardised Estonian corpus), and poetic expressions, structures and content, and there are no parsers, language models, or dictionaries covering this variation. This sets some limits to the potential methods.

Formulas in Finnic oral poetry

In the research of Finnic oral poetry, the idea of formulas was first met with doubt. Finnish folklorist Leea Virtanen (1968: 57–58) noted that normally, a researcher can easily say what poetic line belongs to which poem, and, thus, there were no formulas used as building blocks across different poems. On the other hand, Virtanen (1968: 42) also told about singers who were said to be able to repeat a song after hearing it only once, a feature recognised by Lord to relate to the oral-formulaic composition. Jouko Hautala noted already in 1945 (p. 15–16), on the basis of his knowledge of the tradition, the singers ability to vary their poems and create new ones on the basis of existing verses and episodes. In Soviet Estonia, the runosong researchers faced the issue of verses and motifs repeating in different contexts firsthand as a hurdle in classification of song texts, which in the 1960s developed to a theoretical interest into the use of “stereotypical expressions” of various lengths in composition of runosongs. Ideas similar to the oral-formulaic theory evolved probably independently as the writings of Parry and Lord were not (widely) known nor mentioned in the

¹ Formulaic Intertextuality, Thematic Networks and Poetic Variation across Regional Cultures of Finnic Oral Poetry. Academy of Finland consortium, 2020–2024.

writings, although the mentions of them might have reached the researchers through the writings of either Soviet Russian or Finnish folklorists (Saarlo 2005).

Lauri Harvilahti (1992b: 89) notes that there were many different options for the style of reproduction:

“singers could repeat songs after a single hearing, and compose new songs on a given subject. On the one hand, they claimed to retain their songs in the form they learned them, leaving nothing out and adding nothing new; on the other hand, they admitted as well that variation was permissible. Prominent singers could repeat very traditional standard narratives of the collective heritage, recast these as newer, somewhat more variable wholes, or even create new and original productions.”

He (1992a) also concludes that the formulaic system in Ingrian narrative poetry is very flexible and reproducible: instead of clear-cut formula types it builds on varying formula families and popular formulas that serve as a model for new ones. Frog (2023) has noted that, at the extremes, formulaic structures can be understood to cover several poetic lines (multiforms, formulaic sequences) at one end and only one word in particular metrical position on the other. The concept of formula, as well as that of stereotypic expression, typically presumes the expression to be used in various poetic contexts (Saarlo 2005).

Our analysis starts from the notion of the formulaic character of metrical oral poetry and the wide research history of poetic formulas and variation of oral poetry. Yet, our approach is data driven: we are interested in different kinds of recurrent units that are reachable in our data via computational means, and the relationships of these units to what has been analysed, variably, as formulas, stereotypical expressions, formulaic sequences, parallel sections, multiforms, or motifs (e.g. Foley 1988; Frog & Lamb 2022; Harvilahti 1992a; Saarlo 2005.)

Quantitative experiments

In our first experiment, we aim to recognize formulas consisting of a single line. For this purpose, it would be natural to look at line types with the highest frequency. However, the corpus is characterised by a large degree of variation, due to which equivalent lines often recur in non-identical forms. For example, some variants of the line *Savu saarella palaa* ‘Smoke is burning on the isle’ are listed below (reproduced from Janicki et al. 2023, Table 1):

Savu saarella palavi,
Savu suaressa palaubi,
Mi se savu soarella palavi,
Savu soaressa palauve,
Savu saarella palaa,
Savu suaressa palaa,
Savu soaressa palaubi,
Savu soarella palaabi,
Savu soarell’ on palaabi,
Savu soarella palaa,
Savu saarell’ on paloa
Savubon soarella palaabi,
Savut saarella palavat:
Savupa soarelle palaabi,

In earlier work (Janicki et al. 2023), we have managed to overcome this problem by calculating a similarity measure on line pairs (cosine similarity based on character bigrams²) and clustering the lines based on this measure. For the purpose of similarity computation, the lines are preprocessed (removal of punctuation and digits, lowercasing). The resulting clusters yield a good approximation of groups of ‘equivalent lines’, consisting of the same content words, but with varying spelling and optional function words. Line clusters can thus be taken as a proxy for ‘line type’ for the purpose of frequency calculations.

² More precisely, we represent verses as vectors of frequencies of character bigrams, considering only the 450 bigrams most frequent in the entire corpus. In the current study, we apply the square root function to the frequencies in order to deemphasize repeating bigrams, which often correspond to onomatopoeic or alliterative syllables. Finally, we calculate the cosine similarity between such vectors.

Looking at the list of most frequent line clusters, we quickly realise that there are two possible causes for high frequency: some lines are very general and occur in various contexts, like ___ *vasten vastaeli* ‘___ answered [to someone]’ (with ___ being a variable element, often a general word like ‘father’, ‘mother’, ‘brother’, ‘maiden’ – the lines nonetheless are clustered together). Other high-frequent lines are restricted to a specific text that occurs in the collection in many copies (some children’s rhymes or lullabies) or repeats the line many times (like in certain kinds of charms, e.g. *Pistos* ‘Sting’).

In order to distinguish between the two above-mentioned types, we consider the distribution of a line across different text types. It is very difficult to pinpoint the definition of *text type* for oral poetry as the texts show varying degrees of similarity and there is no way to fix a threshold of what constitutes ‘the same text’. While manually created type indices exist for a large part of our collections, they were done for different principles and with different purposes (mainly search) in mind: especially in the Finnish SKVR corpus, a text is often assigned multiple type names that refer to smaller parts of it, and the type names often group together abstract semantic entities (like ‘a story of a boat journey’, or ‘a charm against iron’), rather than referring to concrete text forms.

Instead, in order to group together identical or similar texts, we apply an automatic clustering of poems based on alignment-based similarity.³ While this does not capture all the similarities of interest (especially among longer texts), it assigns each text to one cluster and ensures that texts in the same cluster are similar in a literal way (containing similar text passages). The poem clustering produced this way is used as a proxy for text type.

We measure the unpredictability of a line’s distribution over text types using entropy – a widely used measure of unpredictability of information introduced by Shannon (1948). If a line occurs $N = n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_k$ times in total, with n_i being the number of occurrences in each of the k different text types, the formula for entropy is:

³ For an explanation of the poem similarity measure and its computation, see Janicki (2023).

$$H(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) = - \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i}{N} \log \frac{n_i}{N}$$

The minimum value of entropy is zero, which is achieved if the distribution is completely predictable (i.e. only one of n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k is non-zero – in our case, if the line only occurs in a single text type). The value is sensitive to both the number of different text types in which the line occurs, as well as to evenness of the distribution – both increase the entropy.

As a line occurring N times in total can maximally occur in N different text types (as each text is assigned one type), maximum entropy for N occurrences is achieved by assuming that each occurrence is in a different type, which yields:

$$H_{max}(N) = - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \log \frac{1}{N} = \log N$$

Dividing the entropy of a distribution by maximally achievable entropy yields *relative entropy*, which tells us how large a portion of the maximum entropy is achieved. This makes it easier to compare distribution of lines with different frequencies, as it puts emphasis of the unevenness of the distribution, rather than the absolute number of possibilities:

$$H_{rel}(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) = \frac{H(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)}{H_{max}(\sum_{i=1}^k n_i)}$$

The following table shows the top-10 and bottom-10 line types wrt. relative entropy, chosen from among the top-1000 most frequent line types. In addition to relative entropy, also the size of the cluster in terms of line tokens (N) and the rank on the list ordered by the number of distinct lines contained (#1 is the largest cluster) is given.

Line (example)	rank	N	H_{rel}	Remarks
Umma majja maräkõnõ	#895	192	0.85	South Estonian: 'a berry [went] into their house' A formula for the singer or some other positive character (metaphorically berry) reaching to home or to some other house.
sanoi sanoilla näillä	#450	255	0.85	Karelia, Finnish & Ingrian: 'said with these words'. A very general formula used in epics, lyrics, wedding songs and charms.

Ütlen uuest' ümber jälle:	#826	333	0.84	North Estonian: 'I will say it anew, in another way'. A formula for starting a new passage that in some way contests or retells the previous one. A conjunctive verse that can be used in the songs of any topic.
Kuule kuule kullakene	#970	169	0.84	Estonian: 'listen, listen, my dear one'. A formula for asking some person to listen. The line cluster includes the examples where the person is specified, for example 'listen, dear son/man/child'. A communicative formula for use in songs of any topic. It is typical to this poetic tradition to call anyone as dear one in addressing verses. Typically to the lines with several alliterative words, there are false positives in the cluster having the same pattern of alliteration but different content.
sinisen salon sisäss,	#632	202	0.83	Karelian, Finnish & Ingrian: "inside the deep blue forest/wilderness", the cluster includes variants like "inside the deep honeyed forest/wilderness", "inside the blue clay/rock", used mostly in charms, epics and lyrics.
Kasa kallis kasvataja.	#207	283	0.83	Mainly South Estonian: 'dear breeder of my husband', in this case, addressing formula towards father-in-law, but the line type includes various addressing towards parents. The line cluster includes also a small number of false positives due to the alliteration (for example <i>kualit kastamatta</i> 'cabbages unwatered').
Kuule, kulla vellekene,	#374	291	0.82	Mostly South Estonian: 'listen, my dear brother'. A version of a general addressing formula, brother can be replaced with other persons (<i>mehekene</i> 'man', <i>külamemmekene</i> 'women from village', etc.).
Tätä päästöä päästämään,	#728	166	0.81	In Karelian, Ingrian and Finnish: "to release this release", more typically "to release this head/end/point", common especially in charms, also in some epics. Some similarly sounding false positives especially in children's songs.
"Oi mie poloinen poika,	#29	697	0.81	Karelian, Ingrian & Finnish: "oh me poor boy", also as 'oh me poor girl' or with varying elements "me

				poor ____". Occurs in a wide variety of lamenting lyrical motifs, frequently embedded in epic stories.
				...
"En anna, ennenkun tuot	#157	276	0	Finnish: "I won't give until you bring [me]" often added with some item to bring. Only in the children's poem type 'Bathing trip of rooster and hen'.
pöperöstä pöytärikki,	#330	315	0	Finnish, Karelian & Ingrian: "from mash (food) a table-tray". Only in a chain song for children <i>Onnimanni</i> in Northern Finnic (another version of the same poem type in Estonia not clustering together).
Palvelin minä talonpoikaa vuoteni	#331	507	0	Finnish and Ingrian-Finnish: 'I served a peasant my due years', in one children's song only.
kaks karujahimeest ka.	#390	232	0	Estonian: 'two bearhunters as well', a refrain line from one song type in newer style.
"Mistä vanha ämmä saap'?" -	#515	276	0	In the Northern Finnic "Where the old woman will get [butter]", in children's song "The mouse goes to the forest" .
rintasolesta sopukka	#730	325	0	Finnic children's poem <i>Onnimanni</i> , Northern Finnic verse type "a nook from a brooch"
Pöytärististä ripuka,	#731	242	0	'A crumb/fringe from a table-cross', <i>Onnimanni</i>
kirjamerkistä meteli,	#784	306	0	'A noise from the book-mark/embroidery', <i>Onnimanni</i>
Sopukasta sormi-kinnas,	#883	246	0	'A finger-mitten from the nook', <i>Onnimanni</i>
"Kyllä mä kalvan katajan juurta."	#922	139	0	'Yes I will gnaw the juniper roots'. From a Northern Finnic version of a children's poem 'A mouse goes to the forest' (the same poem type in Estonian too, but does not cluster together with the Northern Finnic one).

Though the line cluster sizes (N) are similar at the top and at the bottom of the list, sorting by relative entropy reveals very different types of lines. At the top of the list we see very general lines occurring in a variety of contexts, like *sanoi sanoilla näillä* 'said with these words', while at the bottom we see lines connected to a specific texts, mostly children's songs (*Onnimanni* (meaning unclear, might relate to

someone who is happy), *Hiiri metsähän menevi* ‘The mouse goes to the forest’, *Kukon ja kanan saunamatka* ‘Bathing trip of rooster and hen’), which are collected in many similar versions, do not typically chain with other poem types and often involve internal repetition (Saarinen et al. 2023).

We can thus view the relative entropy as a measure of *indexicality*, i.e. degree to which a line points to a specific poem type of text (Frog 2010; Saarinen 2022) – the lower the entropy, the higher the indexicality. In the middle of the list we find formulas occurring in varying texts, but linked to a more specific set of stories, e.g. mentioning the legendary heroes: *Vanha Väinämöinen* ‘old Väinämöinen’ ($H_{rel} = 0.5$), *Se kaunis Kalevan poika* ‘that beautiful son of Kaleva’ ($H_{rel} = 0.5$), *lieto Lemminkäinen* ‘swift Lemminkäinen’ ($H_{rel} = 0.45$), or describing a scene which can appear in different contexts: *"Mis sa nutad, tütar noori?"* (Estonian, $H_{rel} = 0.53$) / *Mitäs itket, tyttäreni*, (Finnish/Karelian, $H_{rel} = 0.52$) ‘Why are you crying, <young/my> daughter’, *Lausui lapsi lattialta* ‘a child spoke from the floor’ ($H_{rel} = 0.52$), *Lämmitti metoisen saunan* ‘warmed up a honeyed sauna’ ($H_{rel} = 0.52$).

Some of these examples actually contain a family of formulas exhibiting a lot of variability, e.g. the sauna to be warmed can be described by different, though metrically and phonetically similar adjectives: *metoinen* ‘honeyed’, *tulinen* ‘fiery’, *äkäinen* ‘irascible’, *haluinen* ‘eager’, *kesoinen* ‘summery’, *kotoinen* ‘homey’, *pyhäinen* ‘sacred/Sunday’, *sotainen* ‘martial’ etc. The cluster including the formula *Lausui lapsi lattialta* ‘a child spoke from the floor’ includes cases like *Vaari lausui lattialta* ‘the old man spoke from the floor’ or *tapa lapsi lattialle* ‘kill the child to the floor’. Thus, the cluster contains shorter than line formulas of the type ‘[someone] spoke from the floor’ and type ‘child on the floor’, and these can also appear together as a line length formula (‘a child spoke from the floor’). In shorter than line formula families, the varying element is usually constrained metrically and the variants are similar either phonetically or semantically. These constraints can thus be seen as part of the formula. Sometimes a set of variants clustered together may have very little elements in common (e.g. only *lattialta*) or even none at all, while it consists of several sub-formulas with more stable elements (e.g. ___ *lausui lattialta* ‘___ spoke from the floor’ with different subjects; or ___ *lapsi lattialta* ‘___ a child from the floor’

with different verbs), linked by variants belonging to both categories, like *lausui lapsi lattialta*.

What determines if a line type can be considered formulaic is, in our understanding, whether the line appears in several poetic contexts. The lines at the beginning of our table mostly represent formulaic line types (line length formulas), at the end of the table there are non-formulaic line types that occur only in the context of a specific song. The border between these two is not strict, and the middle of the table contains more ambiguous cases. It is worth noting that our clusters vary in nature: while some represent clear whole line formulas, others contain a group of line types or line length formulas connected by a shorter than line formula, a wider formula family or a set of related formula families, and some clusters also contain false positives due to the patterns of sound similarity.

Multi-line formulas

As parallelism is a common feature of Finnic oral poetry, formulaic expressions often range over multiple lines – in particular, two-line sequences are common. In order to explore them, we apply a statistical co-occurrence measure called *log-likelihood ratio* (Dunning, 1993; Evert, 2004; Bordag, 2008)⁴, which measures how surprising the number of joint occurrences of two line types is, compared to their individual frequencies. As ‘joint occurrence’ we define a case in which lines are either directly next to each other, or separated by at most 1 other line, as there is some variation in how parallel lines are used.

The log-likelihood ratio statistic has a χ^2 distribution with 1 degree of freedom, meaning that if the co-occurrence of two lines is entirely random, there’s only 5% probability of obtaining a value higher than 3.84 and 0.1% probability of obtaining a value higher than 10.81. These values can be used as a threshold for whether the co-occurrence is statistically significant (whether the hypothesis of independence of lines can be rejected), but in practice they are far too low for a useful interpretation. This is because the independence assumption applies to the entire linguistically and

⁴ Bordag (2008) also mentions a measure called *Lexicographer’s Mutual Information* (LMI), which has a simpler formula than log-likelihood ratio and is often similarly useful. Here we decided to use LLR because of a more meaningful statistical interpretation, but in explorations we often use LMI as well. LMI is also mentioned by Evert (2004, p. 89) under the name *local-MI*.

regionally varied corpus, and in addition to parallelism there are many weaker types of relations between lines that can lead to statistically significant co-occurrence. This is why we are rather interested in the value of log-likelihood ratio as a measure of the strength of relation, than in exceeding a certain threshold for a statistical independence test.

As in the previous experiment, we consider the top-1000 most frequent line types to restrict the analysis to the most frequently recurring units. We consider pairs of co-occurring lines in the order of decreasing LLR (log-likelihood ratio). The results are again a mixture of fragments of specific texts and line combinations occurring in varying contexts. As we find the latter to be more relevant for the analysis of formulaic language, we consider pairs of co-occurring lines with relative entropy (see previous section) > 0.3 . Some hand-picked examples are listed in the table below.

Lines (H_{rel})	LLR	Remarks
Peremees, peremeheke (0.31) Perenaine, naisukene (0.4)	11,385	“Master, dear master”, “Mistress, dear mistress” Estonian and Ingrian verses addressing the host and hostess, common especially in calendrial, narrative and working songs.
yheksän meren yl’itši, (0.54) meri puolen kymmenettä. (0.59)	10,500	“Over the nine seas, half of the tenth sea” Northern Finnic verse pair about a long distance voyage, common in many charms, narrative songs and some songs for children.
Tule työsi tuntemaan (0.35) Pahasi parantamaan (0.39)	9,769	‘Come and get to know your work / Make up for your evil’. Northern Finnic line pair common in charms.
Neitsyt Maria emonen (0.57) Rakas äiti armollinen (0.53)	9,148	An invocation to the Virgin Mary, often used in charms.
Tulli üles hummogul (0.72) Varra inne valgõt! (0.73)	7,561	‘I got up in the morning, early before the daylight’. A typical song-initial formula in Southern Estonian narrative songs.
puhun suulla puhtahalla (0.49) Herran hengellä hyväll’. (0.47)	5,775	‘I’m speaking with pure lips / In the good spirit of the Lord’. Common formula in Northern

		Finnic charms.
___ vanha Väinämöinen, (0.5) Itše tuon sanoiksi virkki: (0.62)	1,357	‘___ the old Väinämöinen / said himself with these words’: element of many Karelian and Eastern Finnish epic stories, with Väinämöinen being the most important epic hero. The first word is variable.

These examples show lines that are strongly connected, mostly bound by parallelism that is regular in this poetic tradition (lines without parallelism occur only occasionally) and specific semantic structure – the parallel lines aim to express the same idea in different words (like *puhun suulla puhtahalla / Herran hengellä hyväll’* ‘I’m speaking with pure lips / In the good spirit of the Lord’). Thus the formulaic units that can be used in various contexts e.g. in this case in various types of charms where an invocation is needed – very often are formed by a pair of parallel lines. This again contrasts with co-occurring low-entropy lines, which are just fragments of a concrete text type, typically a children’s song or a lullaby (not shown).

The pairwise co-occurrences can be used to study longer sequences of lines as well. This can be done by employing network analysis of the graph of co-occurrences. The network structure reveals how lines combine into motifs, form variants (branches) and connect to different contexts. We have explored this kind of analysis on a smaller scale with a selected type of epic story (Sarv et al., in press) and it proved to be informative, giving an overview of the alternative branches of storyline. Any considerable linguistic variation, however, poses the challenge as the variation of content and linguistic form intermingle in the results. In addition the dominant variants tend to rule the outcome, leaving the less-represented, but sometimes important content elements or variants hidden. A large-scale study of this kind is probably not feasible because of the complexity of the corpus, but further explorations in this direction (perhaps with improvements in methods and tools) can contribute to the understanding of recurrent units in oral poetry.

Formulas below line level

As the poetic metre of Finnic oral poetry consists of eight metric positions (usually 7–12 syllables), lines typically contain between 2-4 words. Shorter than line formulas

typically occupy 4–6 metrical positions, corresponding to 2–3 words. Shorter than line formulas (such as “lapsi lattialla” ‘child on the floor’) can also make part of different kinds the whole lines – used only occasionally or only in particular poetic contexts – or whole line formulas used in different contexts (*lausui lapsi lattialla* ‘the child said from the floor’; *pieni lapsi lattielta* ‘small child from the floor’, *ota lapsi lattialta* ‘take the child from the floor’). When the folklorists are using our text search interface, they often make use of the more stable word beginnings of two word formulas (lap* la t*) but here, one needs to consider the appropriate length of the word beginnings and the potentiality of dialectal sound variations case by case.

It is conceivable to apply the same co-occurrence measures as in the previous section to study the co-occurrence of words. However, currently we do not have a way to deal with the variation on the level of individual words, e.g. recognizing that *saarella*, *soaressa* etc. (see the example at the beginning of this section) are occurrences of the same word type. Simple string similarity will not suffice as individual words are short and the number of differing characters can be considerable (e.g. *saarella* ‘on an island’ vs. *suaressa* ‘in an island’), while on the other hand some distinct words can be very similar (e.g. in the line *Selvällä meren selällä* ‘on the bright open sea’, literally ‘on the bright back of the sea’, *selvällä* (on the bright) and *selällä* (on the back) are completely different words). Rule-based approaches and generally available lemmatizers are not applicable because of the diversity and unpredictability of the variation. Initial explorations have shown that restricting the analysis to co-occurrence of word forms (distinguished exactly as they are written) is too fragmentary to be representative of the actual phenomenon. The study of individual words thus remains a question for further work. On the other hand, variants of entire lines contain enough stable elements to be recognized by a simple bigram-based method.

Conclusion

We have provided some starting points for the study of formulaic language in the Finnic oral poetry on a large scale using statistical methods. Based on the earlier work on clustering similar lines and similar texts, we have shown that the entropy of the line type’s distribution over text types allows distinguishing truly formulaic lines

from fragments of frequently repeated stable texts. The approach can be scaled to sequences of lines by studying line co-occurrences. The study of units below the level of line (individual words) remains a challenge for further work due to high linguistic variation. We hope that quantitative studies can contribute to a more precise definition of the term 'formula' and the understanding of its role in oral tradition.

References

- Bordag, Stefan (2008). A Comparison of Co-occurrence and Similarity Measures as Simulations of Context. *Conference on Intelligent Text Processing and Computational Linguistics (CiCLing)*.
- Dunning, Ted (1993). Accurate Methods for the Statistics of Surprise and Coincidence. *Computational Linguistics*, 19(1), pp. 61-74.
- Evert, Stefan (2004). *The Statistics of Word Cooccurrences: Word Pairs and Collocations*. PhD thesis, University of Stuttgart.
- Foley John Miles (1988). *The Theory of Oral Composition: History and Methodology*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Foley, John Miles (1995). *The Singer of the Tales in Performance*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Frog (2010). Multiformit kalevalamittaisessa epiikassa. *Kalevalanmittaisen runon tulkintoja* (eds. S. Knuuttila, U. Piela and L. Tarkka) 91-113. Kalevalaseuran vuosikirja 89. Helsinki.
- Frog. (2022). Multiform theory. In: Frog & Lamb (2022).
- Frog & William Lamb (eds.) (2022). *Weathered Words: Formulaic Language and Verbal Art*. Cambridge, MA: The Milman Parry Collection of Oral Literature, Harvard University.
- Harvilahti, Lauri (1992a). *Kertovan runon keinot. Inkeriläisen runoepiikan tuottamisesta. (Devices of narrative poetry: Producing Ingrian epic poetry.)*, vol. 522 of SKST. Helsinki: SKS.

Harvilahti, Lauri (1992b). The production of Finnish epic poetry – fixed wholes or creative compositions? *Oral Tradition*, 7(1):87–101.

Hautala, Jouko (1945). *Lauri Lappalaisen runo: Vertaileva kansanrunoudentutkimus*. Helsinki: Suomalaisen Kirjallisuuden Seura.

Janicki, Maciej (2023). Large-scale weighted sequence alignment for the study of intertextuality in Finnic oral poetry. *Journal of Data Mining and Digital Humanities*, special issue on Natural Language Processing for Digital Humanities.

Janicki, Maciej, Kati Kallio and Mari Sarv (2023). Exploring Finnic written oral folk poetry through string similarity. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* 38(1): 180-194.

Kallio, Kati, Frog and Mari Sarv. (2017). What to Call the Poetic Form: Kalevala-Meter or Kalevalaic Verse, regivärss, Runosong, the Finnic Tetrameter, Finnic Alliterative Verse, or Something Else? *RMN Newsletter* 12–13: 94–117.

Kallio, Kati, Maciej Janicki, Eetu Mäkelä, Liina Saarlo, Jukka Saarinen and Mari Sarv. (2023). Eteneminen omalla vastuulla. Lähdekriittinen laskennallinen näkökulma sähköisiin kansanrunoaineistoihin. *Elore* 30(1): 59–90. <https://doi.org/10.30666/elore.126008>

Lord, Albert B. (1960). *The Singer of Tales*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press. [Repr. 2000].

Parry, Milman (1930). *Studies in the Epic Technique of Oral Verse-Making. I: Homer and Homeric Style*. *Harvard Studies in Classical Philology* XLI: 73–147.

Reichl, Karl (2022). Formulas in Oral Epics. The Dynamics of Meter, Memory, and Meaning. In: Frog & William Lamb (eds.), *Weathered Words: Formulaic Language and Verbal Art*. Cambridge, MA: The Milman Parry Collection of Oral Literature, Harvard University, 23–47.

Saarinen, Jukka (2022). Formula and structure: Ways of expressing names in the Northern runosong tradition. In: Frog & Lamb (2022).

Saarinen, Jukka, Maciej Janicki and Kati Kallio (2023). Patterned repetition in Finnic oral poetry. In: *Proceedings of Plotting Poetry 6: The Plot. Storytelling in Verse* (in press). Budapest, 2023.

Saarlo, Liina (2005). *Eesti regilaulude stereotüüpiast: Teooria, meetod ja tähendus*. PhD thesis, University of Tartu: Tartu Ülikooli Kirjastus. <http://hdl.handle.net/10062/838>

Sarv, Mari, Kati Kallio and Maciej Janicki (2024). Arvutuslikke vaateid läänemeresoome regilaulude varieeruvusele: Harja otsimine ja Mõök merest. [Computational perspectives on the variability of Finnic runosongs: Searching for the Comb and The Sword from the Sea.] *Keel ja Kirjandus* No 3 (in press).

Shannon, Claude E. (1948). A mathematical theory of communication. *The Bell System Technical Journal* 27:3, pp. 379–423.

Tarkka, Lotte (2017). "Word upon a Word": Parallelism, Meaning, and Emergent Structure in Kalevala-meter Poetry." *Oral Tradition* 31(2): 259–292.

Virtanen, Leea (1968). *Kalevalainen laulutapa Karjalassa*. Suomi 113: 13. Helsinki: SKS.